

The DR3 Milky Way Rotation Curve within the Framework of General Relativity Without Dark Matter

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The GAIA DR3 measurement campaign has produced a MW rotation curve with significantly improved accuracy compared with previous campaigns. In 2023, several authors presented accurate rotation curves calculated from these measurements, within the framework of the dark matter hypothesis. They established new estimates of the Milky Way's dynamical mass of around $2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$. Some of these authors showed that, from a radial distance of around 18 kpc, the Milky Way presents a significant Keplerian decay in the rotation curve, rather than a plateau zone. In this paper, we use a set of data tables from four different authors in a single database. Without making any assumptions about the existence or absence of dark matter, we analyze the observed radial acceleration as a function of the baryonic acceleration. We show that the observed acceleration is an accurate linear function of the baryonic acceleration, making the dark matter hypothesis problematic. Furthermore, we prove that the MW rotation curve can be calculated within the framework of General Relativity without dark matter, using the dynamic metric we published earlier in 2023: "On the incompleteness' of Birkhoff's theorem: A new approach to the central symmetric Gravitational Field in Vacuum Space." In particular, this metric allows us to predict and model the Keplerian decay zone of the rotation curve. Our dynamical mass evaluation does not differ significantly from the value $2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$.

Keywords: Milky way; GAIA; DR3; rotation curve; Schwarzschild; MOND; dark matter; Birkhoff; curvature.

1. Introduction

The GAIA DR3 measurement campaign enabled us to obtain the Milky Way's rotation curve with much greater precision than in previous campaigns. Different analyses of these measurements have detected a Keplerian decay in the rotation curve.

In this paper, we propose to prove that these measurements can be interpreted within the framework of the theory of General Relativity without the presence of dark matter, using a set of equations demonstrated in Ref. 2.

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2. DR3 MW Rotation Curve

We have combined the Milky Way rotation curve tables (cf. Table 20 in Appendix A) provided by Jiao *et al.*,³ Ou *et al.*,⁷ Wang *et al.*¹¹ and Zhou *et al.*,¹² into a single table of 108 data. No changes were made to the table values of the individual papers; double points have not been removed. We obtain the MW rotation curve reported in Fig. 1.

To analyze these data, we will use two kinds of baryonic velocity model: B1 and B2 (for information on the detailed design of these baryonic models see de Salas and Malhan⁸); the B1 curve has been extracted from Fig. 4 in Zhou *et al.*¹²; the B2 curve has been extracted from Fig. 5 in Jiao *et al.*,³ as shown in Fig. 2.

We will present the MW rotation curve in another form, obtained in the $g_{\text{bar}} - g_{\text{obs}}$ plane with $g_{\text{bar}} = \frac{GM_b(r)}{r^2}$ and $g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{V^2}{r}$. G is the universal gravitational constant, r is the radial distance, $M_b(r)$ is the baryonic mass internal to the sphere of radius r (the total baryonic mass is noted M_b (for $r \geq 16.5$ kpc)), V is the orbital velocity of the stars, g_{bar} is the Newtonian radial acceleration and g_{obs} is the observed radial acceleration. We have added in all the following figures (except Figs. 1 and 2) the rotation curve obtained with the McGaugh relation (2.1):

Fig. 1. DR3 MW rotation curve.

Fig. 2. DR3 MW baryonic velocity

$$g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{g_{\text{bar}}}{1 - e^{-\sqrt{g_{\text{bar}}/a_0}}}. \quad (2.1)$$

The constant $a_0 = 1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$ is the Milgrom acceleration constant.⁴ The McGaugh's relation (2.1) has been used for fitting the radial acceleration relation (RAR) to the SPARC database. In their document, Li *et al.*⁴ showed that the McGaugh's relation allows obtaining a tight fit for the rotation curve of 175 individual galaxies in the SPARC database.

3. Modeling the MW Rotation Curve with the B1 Baryonic Model

The curve $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$ plotted in Fig. 3, has been modeled by two straight lines: part 1 for g_{bar} high values and part 2 for g_{bar} low values. In this paper, we will refer to this model as the GR model; the GR correlations are reported in Table 1. Given the large discrepancies between baryonic mass estimates from models B1 and B2 (50%), we will only give empirical values, except for dynamical mass, for which we will give a confidence interval in Sec. 7.2.

The constant a_s is an arbitrary acceleration scale factor, allowing parameters a and b to be obtained with the same order of magnitude. Modeling the rotation curve is very straightforward, requiring no complex assumptions or processing. The extrapolation of the curve for high g_{bar} values will be analyzed as follows (cf. Sec. 7.2).

We will also carry out an analysis in the $\rho - \beta$ plane, defined as follows:

$$\text{Definitions : } V^2 = \frac{GM_b(r)}{R(r)}; \quad \rho = \frac{r}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/a_s}};$$

Fig. 3. DR3 MW rotation curve: $g_{\text{bar}} - g_{\text{obs}}$ plane. Baryonic model: B1.

Table 1. Parameters and functions describing curves of Fig. 3.

Part 1: g_{bar} high values	$g_{\text{obs}} = a g_{\text{bar}} + b \times a_s$
Part 2: g_{bar} low values	$g_{\text{obs}} = d g_{\text{bar}}$
Coefficients	$a = 1.20; b = 0.42; d = 2.40; a_s = 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$
Critical intersection ^a	$g_{\text{bar}_C} = 0.35 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}; g_{\text{obs}_C} = 0.84 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$

^aIntersection of parts 1 and 2.

$$\beta = \frac{R(r)}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/a_s}} \Rightarrow g_{\text{bar}} = \frac{a_s}{\rho^2}; \quad g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{a_s}{\rho\beta}$$

$$\text{GR model : part 1 : } \beta = \frac{\rho}{a + b\rho^2} \Rightarrow \frac{d\beta}{d\rho} = \frac{a - b\rho^2}{(a + b\rho^2)^2}, \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\text{part 2 : } \beta = \frac{\rho}{d} \Rightarrow \frac{d\beta}{d\rho} = \frac{1}{d}, \quad (3.1b)$$

$$\text{part 1 : } \frac{d\beta}{d\rho} = 0 \quad \text{for } \rho = \rho_C = \sqrt{a/b} \cong 1.69 \quad \text{and for}$$

$$g_{\text{bar}} = g_{\text{bar}_C} = \frac{a_s}{\rho_C^2} \cong 0.35 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}. \quad (3.2)$$

β -curves and $d\beta/d\rho$ (GR model) curve are plotted in Figs. 4, 8 and 9; we will also plot in Figs. 4, 8 and 9 the McGaugh's relation written in the $\rho - \beta$ plane:

$$\beta_{\text{McGaugh}} = \rho[1 - e^{-\sqrt{a_s/a_0}/\rho}] \Rightarrow \beta_{\text{McGaugh}} = \rho[1 - e^{-1/(\rho\sqrt{1.2})}].$$

We observe that the singular point where the change in slope of the curve $\beta(\rho)$ occurs is where the derivative $d\beta/d\rho$ cancels; the intersection of the two straight lines occurs for $r = r_C$, $g_{\text{bar}} = g_{\text{bar}_C}$, $\rho = \rho_C$. We will call this singular point the critical point of the rotation curve, defined by the parameters g_{bar_C} , g_{obs_C} , ρ_C , β_C , r_C :

$$\begin{aligned} a g_{\text{bar}_C} + b \times a_s &= d g_{\text{bar}_C} \Rightarrow g_{\text{bar}_C} = \frac{b \times a_s}{d - a} = \frac{a_s}{\rho_C^2} \\ \Rightarrow \rho_C &= \sqrt{(d - a)/b} = \sqrt{a/b} \quad (\text{cf. relations (3.2)}) \Rightarrow d = 2a; \\ \beta_C &= \frac{\rho_C}{a + b\rho_C^2} = \frac{\sqrt{a/b}}{2a} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a \times b}}, \\ g_{\text{bar}_C} &= b \times a_s/a, \end{aligned} \quad (3.3a)$$

Fig. 4. DR3 MW rotation curve: $\rho - \beta$ plane. Baryonic model: B1.

Fig. 5. DR3 MW rotation curve: radius-velocity plane. Baryonic model: B1.

In Fig. 5, the rotation curve is plotted in radius-velocity coordinates

$$g_{\text{obs}C} = 2\mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s, \quad (3.3b)$$

$$\rho_C = \sqrt{\mathbf{a}/\mathbf{b}}, \quad (3.3c)$$

$$\beta_C = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}}}. \quad (3.3d)$$

Only two parameters (\mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b}) are needed to characterize the curve $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$. For the part of the curve corresponding to the g_{bar} low values (part 2), we obtain $g_{\text{obs}} = 2\mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}} \Rightarrow \frac{V^2}{r} = 2\mathbf{a} \frac{GM_b(r_C)}{r^2}$. Thus, in part 2, the rotation curve becomes Newtonian if we assume that the galaxy's mass is no longer equal to its baryonic mass M_b , but equal to a dynamical mass M_{dyn} such that $M_{\text{dyn}} = 2\mathbf{a}M_b$. This result is obtained without making any assumption about the existence or absence of dark matter: whatever assumption we make, the dynamical mass of the galaxy is greater than its baryonic mass, and we obtain for part 2 of the curve $M_{\text{dyn}} \cong 2.40 M_b$. For part 1 of the rotation curve, the dynamical mass $M_{\text{dyn}}(r)$ is obtained from the relation $g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s$ as

$$M_{\text{dyn}}(r) = \mathbf{a}M_b(r) + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s r^2 / G. \quad (3.4)$$

The radial distance r_C to the critical point is defined by the relations $g_{\text{bar}C} = \frac{GM_b(r_C)}{r_C^2} \Rightarrow r_C = \sqrt{\frac{GM_b(r_C)}{g_{\text{bar}C}}}$. For the B1 baryonic model $M_b(r_C) = M_b \cong 0.845 \times 10^{11} M_\odot \Rightarrow r_C \cong 18.3 \text{ kpc} = 58700 \text{ L.Y.}$ The critical point determines the end of the Milky Way, because from this point on, dynamical mass no longer varies with radial distance from the galaxy's center. The diameter of the Milky Way is thus defined as $\approx 36.6 \text{ kpc}$ (117,400 L.Y.).

4. The Dark Matter, MOND and GR Hypotheses

According to the dark matter hypothesis, inside the galaxy, the radial acceleration is defined by the relationship $g_{\text{obs}}(r) = g_{\text{bar}}(r) + g_{\text{DM}}(r)$, where $g_{\text{DM}}(r)$ is the dark matter acceleration. From the preceding results, we obtained the relations:

$$\text{part 1 : } g_{\text{obs}}(r) = 1.20 g_{\text{bar}}(r) + 0.42 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}, \quad (4.1a)$$

$$\text{part 2 : } g_{\text{obs}}(r) = 2.40 g_{\text{bar}}(r), \quad (4.1b)$$

which leads to the relation for hypothetical dark matter:

$$\text{part 1 : } g_{\text{DM}}(r) = 0.20 g_{\text{bar}}(r) + 0.42 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}, \quad (4.2a)$$

$$\text{part 2 : } g_{\text{DM}}(r) = 1.40 g_{\text{bar}}(r). \quad (4.2b)$$

These relations are incompatible with the dark matter hypothesis, since by assumption, dark matter acceleration does not depend on baryonic acceleration. Thus, the DR3 results analyzed with the B1 baryonic model contradict the dark matter hypothesis.

According to this reasoning, the dark matter hypothesis is not valid for MW; consequently, Schwarzschild metric would not be valid to describe our Galaxy's rotation curve. In the event of such an occurrence, different models have been developed outside the framework of General Relativity. One of the best known is Milgrom's MOND model.^{1,5,6,10} McGaugh has proposed a simple formulation of MOND which we presented above (cf. relation (2.1)). We observe in Fig. 3 that the McGaugh formulation used for modeling the SPARC database, for which Li *et al.*⁴ obtained good agreement with the SPARC measurements, is also in good agreement with the modeling of part 1 of the MW rotation curve, which means that the DR3 GAIA measurements, analyzed with the B1 baryonic model, confirm the validity of Milgrom's MOND model up to the critical point, but at the same time they invalidate MOND for radial distances sufficiently far from the center of our Galaxy. MOND's assumption that the plateau zone of the rotation curve is only modified by the action of an external gravitational field (external field effect)^{5,6} is refuted for the Milky Way by the DR3 GAIA tests, since part 2 of the rotation curve is entirely defined by part 1. MOND explains part 1 correctly, but cannot define part 2.

We have developed a new metric, different from the Schwarzschild metric, for the central symmetric gravitation field in vacuum within the framework of General Relativity.² We will show in Sec. 7 that this model explains the DR3 MW rotation curve.

5. Summary of Results Obtained with the B1 Baryonic Model

Table 2 brings together all the numerical values obtained in the previous sections. These values are obtained from four basic quantities: \mathbf{a}_s , \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} , M_b . \mathbf{a}_s is an arbitrary scale factor.

Coefficients \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are obtained from the velocity data in Table 20 and the baryonic velocity curve in model B1. These data are used to calculate test points in the form $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$. These points are plotted in Fig. 3; they are referred to as "gobs Data." If $g_{\text{bar}} \geq g_{\text{bar}_C} : g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s$; if $g_{\text{bar}} < g_{\text{bar}_C} : g_{\text{obs}} = 2\mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}}$, then the linear regressions are plotted as "gobs GR" in Fig. 3.

M_b is the total baryonic mass, deduced from the B1 baryonic model.

Table 2. Parameters and functions of the B1 baryonic model.

Coefficients	$\mathbf{a} \cong 1.20; \mathbf{b} \cong 0.42; \mathbf{a}_s = 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2} (\mathbf{a}_s \text{ is arbitrary})$
Critical point	$\rho_C = \sqrt{\mathbf{a}/\mathbf{b}}; \beta_C = 1/\sqrt{4\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}}; g_{\text{bar}_C} = \mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}/\mathbf{a}; g_{\text{obs}_C} = 2\mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}$
Critical point data	$\rho_C \cong 1.69; \beta_C \cong 0.70; g_{\text{bar}_C} \cong 0.35 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}; g_{\text{obs}_C} \cong 0.84 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$
Baryonic mass	$M_b \cong 0.845 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$ (B1 baryonic model 11)
Critical distance	$r_C = \sqrt{(\mathbf{a} \times GM_b)/(\mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s)} \cong 18.3 \text{ kpc}$ (58700 LY : end of MW)
Dynamical mass	$M_{\text{dyn}} = 2\mathbf{a}M_b \cong 2.03 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$
$g_{\text{bar}} > g_{\text{bar}_C}$	$g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_s$
$g_{\text{bar}} \leq g_{\text{bar}_C}$	$g_{\text{obs}} = 2\mathbf{a} g_{\text{bar}}$
$\rho < \rho_C$	$\beta = \rho/(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\rho^2) \Rightarrow d\beta/d\rho = (\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b}\rho^2)/(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\rho^2)^2$
$\rho \geq \rho_C$	$\beta = \rho/2\mathbf{a} \Rightarrow d\beta/d\rho = 1/2\mathbf{a}$

The parameters $R(r)$, ρ , β are obtained from the definitions as follows:

$$\text{Definitions : } V^2 = \frac{GM_b(r)}{R(r)}; \quad \rho = \frac{r}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}};$$

$$\beta = \frac{R(r)}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}} \Rightarrow g_{\text{bar}} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho^2}; \quad g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho\beta}.$$

The critical point in Table 2 is defined as the point at which the $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$ curve undergoes a change in slope in Fig. 3. The values ρ_C , β_C , g_{bar_C} , g_{obs_C} , r_C are the values of ρ , β , g_{bar} , g_{obs} , r at the critical point.

6. Modeling the MW Rotation Curve with the B2 Baryonic Model

In Fig. 6, the curve $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$ is modeled with three straight line segments. The global curve no longer agrees with McGaugh's relation. In Fig. 7, the rotation curve is plotted in radius-velocity coordinates.

Coefficients \mathbf{a}_1 , \mathbf{b}_1 , \mathbf{a}_2 , \mathbf{b}_2 are obtained from the velocity data in Table 20 and the baryonic velocity curve in model B2. These data are used to calculate test points in the form $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$. These points are plotted in Fig. 6; they are referred to as ‘‘gobs Data.’’ The series of points such that $g_{\text{bar}} \geq g_{\text{bar}_C}$ is modeled by the linear regression

Fig. 6. DR3 MW rotation curve: $g_{\text{bar}} - g_{\text{obs}}$ plane. Baryonic model: B2.

Fig. 7. DR3 MW rotation curve: radius-velocity plane. Baryonic model: B2.

Table 3. Parameters and functions of the B2 baryonic model.

Coefficients	$\mathbf{a}_1 \cong 1.71; \mathbf{b}_1 \cong 0.41; \mathbf{a}_2 \cong 1.22; \mathbf{b}_2 \cong 0.68$
Critical point	$g_{\text{bar}_C} = \mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}_1 / \mathbf{a}_1; g_{\text{obs}_C} = 2\mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}_1$
Intermediate point ^a	$g_{\text{bar}_I} = \mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}_2 / \mathbf{a}_2; g_{\text{obs}_I} = 2\mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}_2$
Critical point data ^b	$g_{\text{bar}_C} \cong 0.24 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}; g_{\text{obs}_C} \cong 0.83 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$
Intermediate point data	$g_{\text{bar}_I} \cong 0.56 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}; g_{\text{obs}_I} \cong 1.37 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$
Total baryonic mass	$M_b \cong 0.60 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$ (B2 baryonic model 3, 8)
Critical distance	$r_C = \sqrt{(\mathbf{a}_1 \times GM_b) / (\mathbf{b}_1 \times \mathbf{a}_s)} \cong 18.6 \text{ kpc}$ (58700 LY. : end of MW)
Dynamical mass	$M_{\text{dyn}} = 2\mathbf{a}_1 M_b \cong 2.05 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$
$g_{\text{bar}} \geq g_{\text{bar}_I}$	$g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}_2 g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_s$
$g_{\text{bar}_C} < g_{\text{bar}} < g_{\text{bar}_I}$	$g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}_1 g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b}_1 \times \mathbf{a}_s$
$g_{\text{bar}} \leq g_{\text{bar}_C}$	$g_{\text{obs}} = 2\mathbf{a}_1 g_{\text{bar}}$

^aConnection between upper and middle line segments; ^bconnection between middle and lower line segments

$g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}_2 g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_s$ (upper line segment). The series of points such that $g_{\text{bar}_C} < g_{\text{bar}} < g_{\text{bar}_I}$ is modeled by the linear regression $g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}_1 g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b}_1 \times \mathbf{a}_s$ (middle line segment). The series of points such that $g_{\text{bar}} \leq g_{\text{bar}_C}$ is modeled by the linear regression $g_{\text{obs}} = 2 \times \mathbf{a}_1 g_{\text{bar}}$ (lower line segment). The linear regressions are plotted as “gobs GR” in Fig. 6.

M_b is the total baryonic mass, deduced from the B2 baryonic model.

The parameters $R(r)\rho, \beta$ are obtained from the definitions as follows:

$$\text{Definitions : } V^2 = \frac{GM_b(r)}{R(r)}; \quad \rho = \frac{r}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}};$$

$$\beta = \frac{R(r)}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}} \Rightarrow g_{\text{bar}} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho^2}; \quad g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho\beta}.$$

The critical point in Table 3 is defined as the point at which the $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$ curve undergoes a change in slope at g_{bar_C} in Fig. 6 (intersection between lower line and middle line). The values $\rho_C, \beta_C, g_{\text{bar}_C}, g_{\text{obs}_C}, r_C$ are the values of $\rho, \beta, g_{\text{bar}}, g_{\text{obs}}, r$ at the critical point. In the case of the dark matter hypothesis, we would obtain: (1) for the upper zone $g_{\text{DM}} = 0.22 \times g_{\text{bar}} + 0.68 \times \mathbf{a}_s$, (2) for the middle zone $g_{\text{DM}} = 0.71 \times g_{\text{bar}} + 0.41 \times \mathbf{a}_s$ and (3) for the lower zone $g_{\text{DM}} = 2.42 \times g_{\text{bar}}$. As in the case of the B1 baryonic

model, the radial acceleration would be a function of baryonic acceleration; again, this result contradicts the basic dark matter hypothesis.

7. Interpretation of Results within the Framework of General Relativity

Although the values of the baryonic masses vary by 50% between hypotheses B1 and B2, the values of the MW dynamical mass and dimension do not vary significantly between the two hypotheses. These values are very close to those obtained by Jiao *et al.*³ and Ou *et al.*⁸ These authors needed to hypothesize and model dark matter to obtain their results. To obtain our results, we made no such assumption. However, we have shown that if we interpret the rotation curve as resulting from the presence of dark matter, the dark matter acceleration is a linear function of the baryonic acceleration, which contradicts the dark matter hypothesis, since dark matter modeling must be independent of baryonic mass.

We observe that, in the case of hypothesis B1, we obtain good agreement between the GR modeling and the McGaugh relation used in MOND, in the zone of the Milky Way where dynamical mass varies (part 1), but the GR and McGaugh relations disagree in the Keplerian zone (part 2), which we have interpreted as external to the Milky Way, the end of the Milky Way being determined to coincide with the end of part 1.

7.1. The non-static version of the Schwarzschild metric

In our previously published paper,² we demonstrated that, despite Birkhoff's theorem, a dynamic solution to the central symmetric gravitational field in vacuum can be defined within the framework of General Relativity. The complete demonstration is reported in Ref. 2. Here is an abbreviated demonstration.

In the mathematical expressions, the t , r exponents represent the partial derivatives with respect to the t , r coordinates; the u , v exponents represent the full derivatives with respect to the u , v functions. By hypothesis, we define the non-static metric by the interval ds :

$$ds^2 = e^{2\lambda(t,r)} dt^2 - e^{2\lambda(t,r)} dr^2 - [R(t,r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2). \quad (7.1)$$

Let us set two arbitrary radial coordinates: r_B and r_M ($r_B < r_M$) and two arbitrary two times differentiable functions: $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$. The solution of the tensor equation $\mathbf{R}_{ij} = 0$, \mathbf{R}_{ij} being the Ricci tensor, is obtained according to the following relations:

$$dz = dR/[1 - R_0/R(t,r)], \quad (7.2)$$

$$u = t + r; \quad v = t - r, \quad (7.3)$$

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) \left(\Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial r^2} = 0 \right), \quad (7.4)$$

$$e^{2\lambda(t,r)} = 4HP^u HM^v [1 - R_0/R(t,r)], \quad (7.5)$$

$$ds^2 = 4HP^u HM^v [1 - R_0/R(t,r)] (dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t,r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2). \quad (7.6)$$

The function $R(t, r)$ is implicitly defined by the relations (7.2) and (7.4). The following mathematical transformations show that it seems possible, *a priori* in all cases to transform the metric (7.6) into the classical Schwarzschild metric. These transformations are made based upon the assumption that they are all justified:

$$ds^2 = 4HP^uHM^v[1 - R_0/R(t, r)]dudv - [R(t, r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (7.7)$$

$$ds^2 = 4[1 - R_0/R(t, r)]dHPdHM - \{R[HP(u) - HM(v)]\}^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (7.8)$$

$$ds^2 = (1 - R_0/R)[(dHP + dHM)^2 - (dHP - dHM)^2] - \{R[HP(u) - HM(v)]\}^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (7.9)$$

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) = R + R_0 \text{Log}|(R/R_0) - 1|. \quad (7.10)$$

By renaming, $HP(u) + HM(v) = t'$ and $HP(u) - HM(v) = r'$, we obtain

$$ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(r')][(dt')^2 - (dr')^2] - [R(r')]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (7.11)$$

$$z = r' = R + R_0 \text{Log}|(R/R_0) - 1|. \quad (7.12)$$

The relations (7.11) and (7.12) define the classical Schwarzschild metric written in tortoise coordinates. The metric (7.6) can be deduced directly from the static metric by inversely performing the operations (7.7) to (7.12). However, in this case, the functions $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ are artificially introduced without any justification. In the complete demonstration (cf. Appendix A in Ref. 2), these functions are required, and are introduced in the solution of a transport equation (cf. Appendix A: relations (A2.7) and (A2.8) in Ref. 2); moreover, in the inverse calculation process, it has not been proven that the metric (7.6) is the only solution of the tensor equation $R_{ij} = 0$ obtained from the metric (7.1).

Finally, for some kinds of functions $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$, the metric (7.6) is broken down into four distinct metrics that replace each other cyclically over time, and for two of the four metrics it is obtained over time an incessant permutation of the spatial/temporal role between the dr and dt coordinate differentials. In this last case, it becomes impossible to perform the coordinate transformations (7.7)–(7.12) allowing to find the classical Schwarzschild metric.

7.2. First integrals of the geodesics in the general case of the non-static metric

Let us set: (1) $\kappa = 1$ for the massive particles or $\kappa = 0$ for the particles without mass; (2) E_r : the energy of the particle; (3) h : the angular momentum of the particle; (4) σ : the proper time of the particle in meters ($\sigma = c\tau$, where c is the speed light (m s^{-1}) and τ is the proper time in seconds) for a massive particle, or an affine parameter for a particle without mass and (5) $w = 1/R$.

The first integrals can be deduced easily from the first integrals of the Schwarzschild metric; however, their direct calculation has been reported in Appendix B of Ref. 2. These first integrals are defined by the following relations,

where R , w , r , t are the coordinates of a massive or without mass particle, according to the κ value:

$$\theta = \pi/2, \quad (7.13)$$

$$R^2 \frac{d\varphi}{d\sigma} = h, \quad (7.14)$$

$$\left(\frac{dR}{d\sigma}\right)^2 + (1 - R_0/R)[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = (E_r)^2, \quad (7.15)$$

$$\frac{d^2w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3w^2 R_0/2 = \kappa R_0/(2h^2), \quad (7.16)$$

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)}, \quad (7.17)$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)}. \quad (7.18)$$

Let us set V_T (in m s^{-1}) the orbital velocity of a massive particle moving along a circular orbit defined by $R = R_s$; we obtain

$$(E_r)^2 = \frac{[1 - R_0/R_s]^2}{[1 - (3/2)R_0/R_s]}, \quad (7.19)$$

$$\frac{(R_s)^2 E_r/h}{(1 - R_0/R_s)} = \frac{R_s \sqrt{R_s}}{\sqrt{GM/c^2}}, \quad (7.20)$$

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R_s)^2 E_r/h}{(1 - R_0/R_s)} \frac{(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v} = \frac{R_s \sqrt{R_s}}{\sqrt{GM/c^2}} \frac{(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v}, \quad (7.21)$$

$$(V_T)^2 = \frac{GM/R_s}{(1 - R_0/R_s)} \frac{4HP^u HM^v}{(HM^v + HP^u)^2}. \quad (7.22)$$

The detailed calculations of these formulas are reported in Appendix B (Secs. 2 and 3) of Ref. 2. The relations (7.13)–(7.16) are identical to the corresponding relations of the classical Schwarzschild metric. The angular deflection of the light rays δ_R is obtained using the formula:

$$\delta_R = 4GM/[c^2 R(t, r)]. \quad (7.23)$$

7.3. Selecting the settings

Let us define (1) a spherical finite space by $r_A \leq r \leq r_B$, where r_A and r_B are two arbitrary radial coordinates, (2) two arbitrary positive numbers ω and α , (3) two functions $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ and (4) the triangular signal $F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(x)$ with pulsation ω (ω in m^{-1}) and amplitude equal to $\frac{\pi}{2\omega}$; its period (in meters) is equal to $Tp = 2\pi/\omega$.

$$F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(x) = -\frac{4}{\pi\omega} \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \frac{\cos(2k+1)\omega x}{(2k+1)^2}. \quad (7.24)$$

Its derivative is the square signal $F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(x)$ with amplitude equal to 1:

$$\frac{dF_{\text{tr}}^\omega(x)}{dx} = F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(x) = \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \frac{\sin(2k+1)\omega x}{(2k+1)}. \tag{7.25}$$

We postulate that the frequency $f = \omega c/2\pi$ is of the order of magnitude of the Planck frequency $F_p = \sqrt{\frac{c^3}{\hbar G}} = 1.855 \times 10^{43}$ Hz (\hbar is the reduced Planck constant), (we would obtain $\omega \sim \frac{2\pi F_p}{c} \Rightarrow$ amplitude of the triangular signal $\sim \frac{l_{\text{Planck}}}{4}$). This assumption is based on the idea that the frequency must be a constant number with a very high value, involving the universal constants G , \hbar , c . We will obtain four oscillation modes (cf. Table 4). At this frequency level, it can be considered that the four oscillation modes are no longer individually discernible, in the case of the geodesic of a large massive particle such as a star. Only the average of these modes, if it is stable, can be physically observed. When the average occurrence of a mode over a time interval $Tp/4$ and a space interval $Tp/4$ is calculated, the occurrence of each mode is found to be equal to 1/4. Consequently, the elements of the average metric can be calculated by performing the sum of the corresponding elements of the metric divided by 4. In the rest of this paper, we will systematically perform this operation to obtain the average metric, considered to be the only observable

$$\text{HP}(u) = r_A + \alpha u/2 + F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(u)/2; \quad \text{HM}(v) = \alpha v/2 + F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(v)/2, \tag{7.26}$$

$$\text{HP}^u = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)]/2; \quad \text{HM}^v = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)]/2, \tag{7.27}$$

$$z = \text{HP}(u) - \text{HM}(v) = r_A + \alpha(u-v)/2 + [F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(u) - F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(v)]/2, \tag{7.28}$$

$$\begin{aligned} dz &= du\text{HP}^u - dv\text{HM}^v = dR/(1 - R_0/R), \\ \Rightarrow dz &= du[\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)]/2 - dv[\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)]/2 = dR/(1 - R_0/R). \end{aligned} \tag{7.29}$$

The metric (7.6) becomes

$$ds^2 = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)][\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)](1 - R_0/R)(dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t, r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \tag{7.30}$$

Let us set: $\Omega^2 = [R(t, r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2)$.

Table 4. Metric $\alpha > 1$ or $\alpha < 1$: step 1.

Mode	Square signals	Metric	dz
1 st	$F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t+r) = 1$ $F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t-r) = 1$	$ds_1^2 = (\alpha + 1)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$
2 nd	$F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t+r) = 1$ $F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t-r) = -1$	$ds_2^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_2 = \alpha dr + dt$
3 rd	$F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t+r) = -1$ $F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t-r) = 1$	$ds_3^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_3 = \alpha dr - dt$
4 th	$F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t+r) = -1$ $F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t-r) = -1$	$ds_4^2 = (\alpha - 1)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$

Table 5. Geodesic $\alpha > 1$ or $\alpha < 1$: step 1.

Mode	Geodesic: A	Geodesic: B
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)}$
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{-(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha-1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha-1)(1-R_0/R)}$

Geodesic relations from relations (7.17), (7.18):

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)};$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)}.$$

Four distinct modes are obtained, depending on the values of the square signals. Tables 4 and 5 (step 1 of the calculations) summarize the properties of the four modes, according to the combination of the square signals:

By performing a convenient coordinates transformation on dt and dr we can verify that each mode, considered alone, can be deduced from the Schwarzschild metric:

$$\{ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t, r)][(dt')^2 - (dr')^2] - \Omega^2; \quad dz = dr'\}.$$

We obtain two kinds of solution, depending on whether $\alpha > 1$ or $\alpha < 1$.

7.4. First case: The non-static metric for $\alpha > 1$

For the circular geodesics of a large massive particle, we set: $dr = 0$; hence Tables 6 and 7 deduced from Tables 4 and 5.

The variable w is defined by the equation: $\frac{d^2 w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3w^2 R_0/2 = R_0/(2h^2)$; this equation is verified approximately by the relations $\frac{dw}{d\varphi} = \pm \frac{E_r}{\alpha h}$ considered on a very short time, by taking into account the relation ($\omega \gg \pi/2$); on average over the four modes, we obtain $dw/d\varphi = 0$.

We set, for the time-averaged terms: $[dz]_{av} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=4} \frac{dz_i}{4}$; $[\frac{d\varphi}{dt}]_{av} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=4} \frac{1}{4} [\frac{d\varphi}{dt}]_i$; $[ds^2]_{av} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=4} \frac{(ds^2)_i}{4}$.

$$[dz]_{av} = \frac{(\alpha dr + dr) + (\alpha dr + dt) + (\alpha dr - dt) + (\alpha dr - dr)}{4} = \alpha dr, \tag{7.31}$$

Table 6. Metric $\alpha > 1$: Final state.

Mode	Metric	dz
1 st	$ds_1^2 = (\alpha + 1)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$
2 nd	$ds_2^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_2 = \alpha dr + dt$
3 rd	$ds_3^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_3 = \alpha dr - dt$
4 th	$ds_4^2 = (\alpha - 1)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$

Table 7. Circular Geodesic $\alpha > 1$: Final state.

Mode	Geodesic A	Geodesic B: $dr/d\varphi = 0$	$w = 1/R$
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$dR/d\varphi = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = 0$
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{\alpha(1-R_0/R)}$	$(R^2 E_r/h) - (dR/d\varphi)\alpha = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = -\frac{E_r}{\alpha h}$
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{\alpha(1-R_0/R)}$	$(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{E_r}{\alpha h}$
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha-1)(1-R_0/R)}$	$dR/d\varphi = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = 0$

$$\Rightarrow \left[\frac{d\varphi}{dt}\right]_{av} = \frac{(\alpha + 1) + 2\alpha + (\alpha - 1) (1 - R_0/R_{av})}{4 (R_{av})^2 E_r/h} = \alpha \frac{(1 - R_0/R_{av})}{(R_{av})^2 E_r/h} \tag{7.32}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left[\frac{d\varphi}{\alpha dt}\right]_{av} = \frac{(1 - R_0/R_{av})}{(R_{av})^2 E_r/h},$$

$$[ds^2]_{av} = \frac{(\alpha + 1)^2 + 2(\alpha^2 - 1) + (\alpha - 1)^2}{4} [1 - R_0/R_{av}(r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$$

$$\Rightarrow [ds^2]_{av} = [1 - R_0/R_{av}(r)][(\alpha dt)^2 - (\alpha dr)^2] - [R_{av}(r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \tag{7.33}$$

$$[dz]_{av} = \alpha dr = \frac{dR_{av}}{(1 - R_0/R_{av})}. \tag{7.34}$$

The average metric defined by the relations (7.33) and (7.34) is the Schwarzschild metric, written in tortoise coordinates. Consequently, if $\alpha > 1$, the metric (7.30) is the Schwarzschild metric.

7.5. Second case: The non-static metric for $\alpha < 1$

We rewrite Tables 4 and 5 in Tables 8 and 9 with a few scheduling changes (step 2 of the calculations):

Table 8. Metric $\alpha < 1$: step 2.

Mode	Square signals	Metric	dz	Symbols
1 st	$F_{sq}^\omega(t + r) = 1$	$ds_1^2 = (1 + \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)]$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$	dt : temporal
	$F_{sq}^\omega(t - r) = 1$	$\times (dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$		dr : spatial
2 nd	$F_{sq}^\omega(t + r) = 1$	$ds_2^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)]$	$dz_2 = \alpha dr + dt$	dt : spatial
	$F_{sq}^\omega(t - r) = -1$	$\times (dr^2 - dt^2) - \Omega^2$		dr : temporal
3 rd	$F_{sq}^\omega(t + r) = -1$	$ds_3^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)]$	$dz_3 = \alpha dr - dt$	dt : spatial
	$F_{sq}^\omega(t - r) = 1$	$\times (dr^2 - dt^2) - \Omega^2$		dr : temporal
4 th	$F_{sq}^\omega(t + r) = -1$	$ds_4^2 = (1 - \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)]$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$	dt : temporal
	$F_{sq}^\omega(t - r) = -1$	$\times (dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$		dr : spatial

Table 9. Geodesic $\alpha < 1$: step 2.

Mode	Geodesic: A	Geodesic: B	Symbols
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) - (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : spatial <i>dr</i> : temporal
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : spatial <i>dr</i> : temporal
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial

Table 10. Metric $\alpha < 1$: step 3.

Mode	Metric	<i>dz</i>	Symbols
1 st	$ds_1^2 = (1+\alpha)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
2 nd	$ds_2^2 = (1-\alpha^2)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_2 = \alpha dt + dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
3 rd	$ds_3^2 = (1-\alpha^2)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_3 = \alpha dt - dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
4 th	$ds_4^2 = (1-\alpha)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial

Table 11. Geodesic $\alpha < 1$: step 3.

Mode	Geodesic: A	Geodesic: B	Symbols
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) - (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial

Table 12. Metric $\alpha < 1$: step 4.

Mode	Metric	<i>dz</i>	Symbols
1 st	$ds_1^2 = (1+\alpha)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
2 nd	$ds_2^2 = (1-\alpha^2)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_2 = \alpha dt + dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
3 rd	$ds_3^2 = (1-\alpha^2)[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_3 = -\alpha dt - dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
4 th	$ds_4^2 = (1-\alpha)^2[1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial

Table 13. Geodesic $\alpha < 1$: step 4.

Mode	Geodesic: A	Geodesic: B	Symbols
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) - (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha^2)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$\left[\frac{dr}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	<i>dt</i> : temporal <i>dr</i> : spatial

By homogenizing the coordinate symbols to obtain in all modes *dt* as the temporal differential and *dr* as the spatial differential, we obtain Tables 10 and 11 (step 3 of the calculations):

The differentials of the temporal coordinates must be aligned with real time, because we have to take into account the first integral: $R^2 \frac{d\varphi}{d\sigma} = h \Rightarrow$ variation of the angle φ with respect to the proper time is monotonic. Then, we have to change the sign of the temporal coordinate differentials in the third and fourth modes to align them with the first mode unchanged that we set as the reference mode. Hence we obtain Tables 12 and 13 (step 4 of the calculations).

We can see that the change in sign of *dt* for the third metric not only regularized the sign of *dt/dφ*, but also stabilized the average of *dz_i*. Without this change of sign, the average would have diverged over time.

For the circular geodesics of a large massive particle, let us set: *dr* = 0. Tables 14 and 15 summarize the properties of the metric:

Table 14. Metric $\alpha < 1$: Final state.

Mode	Metric	<i>dz</i>
1 st	$ds_1^2 = (1 + \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_1 = \alpha dr + dr$
2 nd	$ds_2^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_2 = \alpha dt + dr$
3 rd	$ds_3^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_3 = -\alpha dt - dr$
4 th	$ds_4^2 = (1 - \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$	$dz_4 = \alpha dr - dr$

Table 15. Circular Geodesic $\alpha < 1$: Final state.

Mode	Circular geodesic: A	Circular geodesic: B	$w = 1/R$
1 st	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1+\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$(dR/d\varphi) = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_1 = 0$
2 nd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)}$	$(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi) = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_2 = -\frac{\alpha E_r}{h}$
3 rd	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)}$	$(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi) = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_3 = \frac{\alpha E_r}{h}$
4 th	$\left[\frac{dt}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)}$	$(dR/d\varphi) = 0$	$\left[\frac{dw}{d\varphi}\right]_4 = 0$

The variable w is defined by the equation: $\frac{d^2w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3w^2R_0/2 = R_0/(2h^2)$; this equation is verified approximately by the relations $\frac{dw}{d\varphi} = \mp \frac{\alpha E_r}{h}$ considered for a very short time, by taking into account the relation ($\omega \gg \pi/2$); on average over time: $dw/d\varphi = 0$.

We obtain, for the time-averaged terms: $[dz]_{\text{av}}, [\frac{d\varphi}{dt}]_{\text{av}}, [ds^2]_{\text{av}}$:

$$[dz]_{\text{av}} = \frac{(\alpha dr + dr) + (\alpha dt + dr) + (-\alpha dt - dr) + (\alpha dr - dr)}{4} = \frac{\alpha}{2} dr, \quad (7.35)$$

$$\left[\frac{d\varphi}{dt}\right]_{\text{av}} = \frac{(1+\alpha) + 2 + (1-\alpha)}{4} \frac{(1-R_0/R_{\text{av}})}{(R_{\text{av}})^2 E_r/h} \Rightarrow \left[\frac{d\varphi}{dt}\right]_{\text{av}} = \frac{(1-R_0/R_{\text{av}})}{(R_{\text{av}})^2 E_r/h}, \quad (7.36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [ds^2]_{\text{av}} &= \frac{(1+\alpha)^2 + 2(1-\alpha^2) + (1-\alpha)^2}{4} [1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \\ \Rightarrow [ds^2]_{\text{av}} &= [1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R_{\text{av}}(r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \end{aligned} \quad (7.37)$$

$$[dz]_{\text{av}} = \frac{\alpha}{2} dr = \frac{dR_{\text{av}}}{(1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}})} \quad (0 \leq \alpha < 1). \quad (7.38)$$

The average metric defined by the relations (7.37) and (7.38) is not the Schwarzschild metric. We will use this metric to model the transition zone of the galaxy rotation curve, between the Schwarzschild zone and the asymptotic zone.

The real time differential interval dT between two events located at (r, θ, ϕ) is

$$c dT = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r)} dt \approx dt \quad (\text{case : } R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r) \ll 1). \quad (7.39)$$

The real radial distance differential interval dL_r is

$$dL_r = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r)} dr \approx dr \quad (\text{case : } R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r) \ll 1). \quad (7.40)$$

From relation (7.38), we obtain $dr = (2/\alpha)dR_{\text{av}}/(1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}})$. From relation (7.40), we obtain

$$dL_r \approx \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}\right) dR_{\text{av}} \quad (\text{case : } R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r) \ll 1). \quad (7.41)$$

From relations (7.21) and (7.36), we obtain on average: $[\frac{d\varphi}{dt}]_{\text{av}} = \frac{\sqrt{GM}/c^2}{R_{\text{av}}(r)\sqrt{R_{\text{av}}(r)}}$. The orbital velocity V of a massive particle located on a circular orbit defined by $R_{\text{av}}(r)$ is defined by the relation:

$$V^2 = \frac{GM/R_{\text{av}}(r)}{1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}(r)}, \quad (7.42)$$

$$\alpha > 1 \Rightarrow dR_{\text{av}}/(1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}) = dr; \quad (7.43a)$$

$$0 \leq \alpha < 1 \Rightarrow dR_{\text{av}}/(1 - R_0/R_{\text{av}}) = (\alpha/2)dr. \quad (7.43b)$$

Conjectures generalizing the formulas (7.43a), (7.43b):

Two generalizations of the formulas (7.43a), (7.43b) have been conjectured in Ref. 2.

First conjecture: we assumed that the formulations (7.43a), (7.43b) could be generalized to the case of a mass varying with distance in the following form:

$$\text{Definitions : } \rho = \frac{r}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}}, \quad (7.44a)$$

$$\beta = \frac{R_{av}(r)}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}}, \quad (7.44b)$$

$$\Rightarrow g_{bar} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho^2}, \quad (7.44c)$$

$$g_{obs} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho\beta}. \quad (7.44d)$$

$M_b(r)$ is equal to the baryonic mass contained in the sphere of radius r (we assimilate r to the real distance, given the large distances occurring in galaxies). In this case, the formulas (7.43a), (7.43b) are generalized to the following form, for large values of r :

$$\alpha > 1 \Rightarrow d\beta = d\rho, \quad (7.45a)$$

$$0 \leq \alpha < 1 \Rightarrow d\beta = (\alpha/2)d\rho. \quad (7.45b)$$

Second conjecture: The formula (7.38) is demonstrated only in the case where the parameter α is a constant. For real applications, it is necessary to make the assumption that α is a function of the form $\alpha(\rho, \beta)$. Hence the following global conjecture, generalization of the relations (7.43a), (7.43b) for large distances:

$$\alpha(\rho, \beta) > 1 \Rightarrow d\beta = d\rho, \quad (7.46a)$$

$$0 \leq \alpha(\rho, \beta) < 1 \Rightarrow d\beta = [\alpha(\rho, \beta)/2]d\rho. \quad (7.46b)$$

From relation (7.46b) we deduce:

$$\text{if } 0 \leq \alpha(\rho, \beta) < 1 \Rightarrow 0 \leq d\beta/d\rho \leq 1/2. \quad (7.47)$$

We transform the inequality (7.47) to obtain its equivalent form in variables g_{bar} , g_{obs} ; we thus obtain

$$\text{if } 0 \leq \alpha(\rho, \beta) < 1 \text{ and } d\beta/d\rho \geq 0 \Rightarrow 2dg_{obs}/dg_{bar} \geq g_{obs}/g_{bar}. \quad (7.48)$$

The solution derived from relation (7.46b) describes a central symmetrical gravitational field in vacuum, in which the space-time curvature oscillates continuously. This oscillation is maintained by the phenomenon of temporal/spatial role exchange between the coordinates differentials dt and dr . Due to this oscillation, the dynamical mass becomes greater than the baryonic mass, without this involving physical matter different from the baryonic matter. The increase in dynamical mass stops if the condition: $d\beta/d\rho \geq 0$ is not satisfied.

There is a special case for relations (7.46a), (7.46b), and that is the case where $\alpha(\rho, \beta)$ crosses the value 1 from the value 1^+ to the value 1^- . In this case, the relations (7.46a), (7.46b) show that there is a discontinuity in the derivative $d\beta/d\rho$. If $\alpha = 1^+$, $d\beta/d\rho = 1$, if $\alpha = 1^-$, $d\beta/d\rho = 1/2$. We will show that this particular case is encountered when we want to complete the Milky Way's rotation curve for all values of radial distance.

7.6. Application to the MW rotation curve

We saw in Sec. 3 that the first relation defining the Milky Way's rotation curve is $g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_S$. From relation (7.48), we deduce $2\mathbf{a} > (\mathbf{a}g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_S)/g_{\text{bar}} \Rightarrow g_{\text{bar}} \geq \mathbf{a}_S \times \mathbf{b}/\mathbf{a}$. For $g_{\text{bar}} < \mathbf{a}_S \times \mathbf{b}/\mathbf{a}$, the relation $g_{\text{obs}}(g_{\text{bar}})$ must change. As $g_{\text{bar}C} = \mathbf{a}_S \times \mathbf{b}/\mathbf{a}$, we find that this change takes place at the critical point. As long as the relation $g_{\text{obs}} = \mathbf{a}g_{\text{bar}} + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_S$ is valid, the dynamical mass M_{dyn} increases with radial distance r according to the relation: $M_{\text{dyn}}(r) = \mathbf{a}M_b(r) + \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{a}_S r^2/G$. The physical impossibility of obtaining the inequality: $d\beta/d\rho < 0$ results in a sudden halt in the growth of the dynamical mass, which reaches its upper limit: $M_{\text{dyn}} = 2\mathbf{a}M_b$ at the critical point. As the dynamical mass becomes constant, the gravitational field of our Galaxy becomes, for distances $r > r_C$, a Newtonian gravitational field whose central mass is $M_{\text{dyn}} = 2\mathbf{a}M_b$.

We can calculate the dynamical mass of the Milky Way using the relationship: $M_{\text{dyn}} = rV^2/G$, averaged over the 39 data points obtained for $r > r_C$ ($r_C = 18.3$ kpc); we obtain $M_{\text{dyn}} = 2.01^{+0.04}_{-0.04} \times 10^{11} M_\odot$. According to Table 4 in Jiao *et al.*,³ average dynamical mass is obtained as $M_{\text{dyn}} = 1.99^{+0.09}_{-0.06} \times 10^{11} M_\odot$; Ou *et al.*⁷ obtained as $M_{\text{dyn}} = 2.13^{+0.17}_{-0.12} \times 10^{11} M_\odot$. All these values are not significantly different.

In Fig. 8 is plotted the complete rotation curve in the ρ - β plane. The third zone (partially) and the fourth zone were previously defined in Sec. 3. The beginning of the third zone is defined by the upper value 1/2 of the derivative $d\beta/d\rho$. Indeed, in this zone, as $\beta < \rho$ (we are outside Schwarzschild zone), this derivative $d\beta/d\rho$ cannot be greater than 1/2, as we saw above. Thus, the formulation of the second zone is

Fig. 8. DR3 MW complete rotation curve: ρ - β plane. Baryonic model: B1.

Table 16. β and g_{obs} functions.

Zone	r -interval	ρ -interval	β	g_{bar} -interval	g_{obs}
1 st	$0 \leq r < r_S$	$0 \leq \rho < \rho_S$	$\beta = \rho$	$g_{bar} > g_{bar_S}$	$g_{obs} = g_{bar}$
2 nd	$r_S \leq r < r_T$	$\rho_S \leq \rho < \rho_T$	$\beta = \frac{\rho + \rho_S}{2}$	$g_{bar_T} < g_{bar} \leq g_{bar_S}$	$g_{obs} = \frac{2g_{bar}}{1 + \sqrt{g_{bar}/g_{bar_S}}}$
3 rd	$r_T \leq r < r_C$	$\rho_T \leq \rho < \rho_C$	$\beta = \frac{\rho}{a + b\rho^2}$	$g_{bar_C} < g_{bar} \leq g_{bar_T}$	$g_{obs} = a g_{bar} + b \times a_s$
4 th	$r \geq r_C$	$\rho \geq \rho_C$	$\beta = \rho/2a$	$g_{bar} \leq g_{bar_C}$	$g_{obs} = 2a g_{bar}$

Table 17. Intermediate points location.

kpc	—	—	ms^{-2}	ms^{-2}
$r_S = \sqrt{GM_b(r_S)}/g_{bar_S}$	$\rho_S = 2\beta_T - \rho_T$	$\beta_S = \rho_S$	$g_{bar_S} = a_s/\rho_S^2$	$g_{obs_S} = g_{bar_S}$
$r_T = \sqrt{GM_b(r_T)}/g_{bar_T}$	$\rho_T = \sqrt{\frac{1+4a-1-a}{b}}$	$\beta_T = \frac{\rho_T}{a+b\rho_T^2}$	$g_{bar_T} = \frac{a_s}{\rho_T^2}$	$g_{obs_T} = \frac{a_s}{\rho_T\beta_T}$
$r_C = \sqrt{(a \times GM_b)/(b \times a_s)}$	$\rho_C = \sqrt{a/b}$	$\beta_C = 1/\sqrt{4a \times b}$	$g_{bar_C} = a_s \times b/a$	$g_{obs_C} = 2a_s \times b$

defined by the relation: $d\beta/d\rho = 1/2$. This second zone begins (at low values) when we obtain $\beta = \rho$: which corresponds to the Schwarzschild solution. The first zone is then the Schwarzschild zone, defined by the relation: $d\beta/d\rho = 1$.

Tables 16–18 summarize the relationships defining the complete rotation curve (baryonic model B1). The interface between zone 1 and zone 2 is noted with the index $S(r_S, \rho_S, g_{bar_S}, g_{obs_S})$ the interface between zone 2 and zone 3 is noted with the index $T(r_T, \rho_T, g_{bar_T}, g_{obs_T})$, the interface between zone 3 and zone 4 is

Table 18. Intermediate points location values.

kpc	—	—	ms^{-2}	ms^{-2}
$r_S = 1.58$	$\rho_S = 0.30$	$\beta_S = 0.30$	$g_{bar_S} = 11.0 \times 10^{-10}$	$g_{obs_S} = 11.0 \times 10^{-10}$
$r_T = 6.90$	$\rho_T = 0.70$	$\beta_T = 0.50$	$g_{bar_T} = 1.77 \times 10^{-10}$	$g_{obs_T} = 2.54 \times 10^{-10}$
$r_C = 18.3$	$\rho_C = 1.69$	$\beta_C = 0.70$	$g_{bar_C} = 0.35 \times 10^{-10}$	$g_{obs_C} = 0.84 \times 10^{-10}$

Fig. 9. DR3 MW complete rotation curve: $r - \beta$ plane. Baryonic model: B1.

Fig. 10. DR3 MW complete rotation curve: r-velocity plane. Baryonic model: B1.

noted with the index $_C(r_C, \rho_C, g_{\text{bar}_C}, g_{\text{obs}_C})$. The complete rotation curve is plotted in $(r - \beta)$ coordinates (Fig. 9) and in $(r\text{-velocity})$ coordinates (Fig. 10).

Our reasoning, carried out within the framework of General Relativity, fully explains the experimental DR3 MW rotation curve described in Sec. 3, and allows us to model the complete rotation curve of our Galaxy.

7.7. Relation between MOND and the GR model

Analysis of the DR3 measurements with the B1 baryonic model showed that the McGaugh correlation agrees with the B1 model of baryonic velocity up to the critical point defining the end of the Milky Way. This suggests a relationship between the Milgrom constant \mathbf{a}_0 and the two GR model constants \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . Using McGaugh's formula $g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{g_{\text{bar}}}{1 - e^{-\sqrt{g_{\text{bar}}/a_0}}}$ at the critical point, we can define an approximate value of \mathbf{a}_0 using the relation: $g_{\text{obs}_C} = \frac{g_{\text{bar}_C}}{1 - e^{-\sqrt{g_{\text{bar}_C}/a_0}}}$. We thus obtain the following value:

$$\mathbf{a}_0 = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}}{\mathbf{a}[\text{Log}(1 - 1/(2\mathbf{a}))]^2} = 1.20 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$$

An empirical form is $\mathbf{a}_0 = \mathbf{a}_s \times \mathbf{b}(4\mathbf{a} - 1.94) = 1.20 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$.

8. Conclusions

The GAIA DR3 campaign has enabled to acquire measurements with much improved accuracy. Using a set of measurements from four different authors, we were able to demonstrate, with our empirical GR model, that inside the Milky Way the observed radial acceleration is a linear function of the baryonic acceleration.

This observation calls into question the dark matter model, since our calculation leads to a dark matter acceleration entirely defined by the baryonic acceleration, thus contradicting the hypothesis of the existence of dark matter independent of baryonic matter.

Our analysis with the B1 baryonic velocity model shows partial agreement with the MOND theory, modeled with the McGaugh formula. The GR and MOND

rotation curves are very close in the Milky Way domain up to 18.3 kpc from the center of our Galaxy. Beyond this point, the models diverge sharply, with the GR model describing a Keplerian decay, while the McGaugh formula describes a plateau zone; MOND's assumption that the central gravitational field is modified by an external field effect appears unsuitable, since according to our calculations the Keplerian decay appears to be entirely predicted by the rotation curve internal to the Milky Way.

We previously published a paper,² in which we showed that, in contradiction to Birkhoff's theorem, at least one solution of the central symmetric gravitational field in vacuum different from the Schwarzschild metric could be found within the framework of General Relativity. This solution is dynamic: space-time curvature is oscillatory; an approximate static solution, described in Sec. 7, can be deduced from this dynamical solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Definitions : } \rho &= \frac{r}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}}; & \beta &= \frac{R_{av}(r)}{\sqrt{GM_b(r)/\mathbf{a}_s}} \Rightarrow g_{bar} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho^2}; \\ g_{obs} &= \frac{\mathbf{a}_s}{\rho\beta}; & V^2 &= \frac{GM_b(r)}{R_{av}(r)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We deduced the static solution : } \alpha(\rho, \beta) > 1 &\Rightarrow d\beta = d\rho; \\ 0 \leq \alpha(\rho, \beta) < 1 &\Rightarrow d\beta = \alpha(\rho, \beta)/2d\rho \end{aligned}$$

Table 19 summarizes the DR3 Milky Way solution. The input data are the baryonic model B1 and Table 20, which are used to calculate \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} ; all the parameters in Table 19 are derived exclusively from \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} .

We find that our empirical GR model of the Milky Way agrees with this solution derived exclusively within the framework of General Relativity. In particular, the stability criterion in the equations ($\alpha(\rho, \beta) \geq 0$) predicts the end of the Milky Way's extension, as well as the resulting change in modeling, resulting in the appearance of the observed Keplerian decay. We consider this result to be particularly important, as it helps to confirm the physical validity of our dynamic metric and its static approximation.

We therefore conclude that, in the case of the Milky Way, the dark matter hypothesis is not appropriate. Our solution and MOND are in agreement throughout the area preceding the Keplerian domain; however MOND's assumption that General Relativity cannot explain the rotation curve of galaxies is challenged both

Table 19. GR model β -function.

ρ -interval	$\alpha(\rho, \beta)$	β
$0 \leq \rho < \rho_S$	1^+	$\beta = \rho$
$\rho_S < \rho < \rho_T$	1^-	$\beta = (\rho + \rho_S)/2$
$\rho_T \leq \rho < \rho_C$	$2(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b}\rho^2)/(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\rho^2)^2$	$\beta = \rho/(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\rho^2)$
$\rho > \rho_C$	$1/\mathbf{a}$	$\beta = \rho/2\mathbf{a}$

theoretically by the existence of our dynamic metric, and practically by the agreement of this metric with GAIA DR3 measurements. Further, our model explains Keplerian decay without requiring an external field effect. According to Sanders⁹ (Sec. 1 page 2): “However, in the context of MOND, the aspect of an asymptotically flat rotation curve is absolute. MOND leaves rather little room for maneuver; the idea is in principle falsifiable, or at least it is far more fragile than the dark matter hypothesis. Unambiguous examples of rotation curves (of isolated galaxies) which decline in a Keplerian fashion at a large distance from the visible object would falsify the idea.”

Appendix A

Table 20. Measurements of the circular velocity of the Milky Way.

Pt	Author	kpc	km/s	Pt	Author	kpc	km/s	Pt	Author	kpc	km/s
1	Zhou	5.24	225.1	37	Ou	12.73	225.61	73	Ou	18.73	210.89
2	Zhou	5.74	233.53	38	Zhou	12.74	225.56	74	Zhou	18.9	212.1
3	Zhou	6.25	234.3	39	Ou	13.22	224.95	75	Ou	19.22	208.48
4	Ou	6.27	231.07	40	Zhou	13.25	224.9	76	Jiao	19.5	206.25
5	Zhou	6.77	233.17	41	Jiao	13.5	224.16	77	Wang	19.5	205.4
6	Ou	6.78	230.93	42	Wang	13.5	224.1	78	Zhou	19.5	210.46
7	Zhou	7.23	236.19	43	Ou	13.72	222.79	79	Ou	19.71	205.97
8	Ou	7.28	232.87	44	Zhou	13.74	223.57	80	Ou	20.22	202.97
9	Zhou	7.83	236	45	Ou	14.22	222.13	81	Zhou	20.41	206.69
10	Ou	7.86	234.14	46	Zhou	14.23	221.1	82	Jiao	20.5	202.54
11	Ou	8.19	232.83	47	Jiao	14.5	221.6	83	Wang	20.5	201.8
12	Zhou	8.21	233.19	48	Wang	14.5	220.7	84	Ou	20.72	195.16
13	Ou	8.71	231.27	49	Ou	14.73	220.08	85	Ou	21.22	200.2
14	Zhou	8.78	233.15	50	Zhou	14.74	220.19	86	Zhou	21.28	207.71
15	Ou	9.23	230.47	51	Zhou	15.23	219.59	87	Jiao	21.5	197.56
16	Zhou	9.26	232.15	52	Ou	15.24	218.25	88	Wang	21.5	198.4
17	Jiao	9.5	221.75	53	Jiao	15.5	218.79	89	Ou	21.72	201.11
18	Wang	9.5	221.3	54	Wang	15.5	218.1	90	Ou	22.27	196.79
19	Ou	9.72	229.16	55	Ou	15.72	221.16	91	Zhou	22.39	203.72
20	Zhou	9.75	231.24	56	Zhou	15.74	217.36	92	Jiao	22.5	197
21	Ou	10.24	229.37	57	Ou	16.24	218.3	93	Wang	22.5	194.3
22	Zhou	10.25	230.34	58	Zhou	16.24	216.61	94	Ou	22.71	218.65
23	Jiao	10.5	223.32	59	Jiao	16.5	216.38	95	Zhou	23.16	205.2
24	Wang	10.5	222.6	60	Wang	16.5	215.5	96	Ou	23.4	192.49
25	Ou	10.74	227.95	61	Zhou	16.74	217.28	97	Jiao	23.5	191.62
26	Zhou	10.75	230.54	62	Ou	16.77	217.07	98	Wang	23.5	193.7
27	OU	11.23	227.09	63	Ou	17.21	219.56	99	Zhou	24	200.64
28	Zhou	11.25	229.11	64	Zhou	17.23	216.25	100	Jiao	24.5	187.12
29	Jiao	11.5	220.72	65	Jiao	17.5	213.48	101	Wang	24.5	194.4
30	Wang	11.5	220.5	66	Wang	17.5	213	102	Ou	25.02	191.48
31	Ou	11.73	227.15	67	Zhou	17.74	213.81	103	Jiao	25.5	181.44
32	Zhou	11.75	227.48	68	Ou	17.77	215.49	104	Wang	25.5	178.5
33	Ou	12.23	226.9	69	Ou	18.23	214.62	105	Jiao	26.5	175.68
34	Zhou	12.24	226.69	70	Zhou	18.35	217.53	106	Wang	26.5	175.5
35	Jiao	12.5	222.92	71	Jiao	18.5	209.17	107	Ou	27.31	172.98
36	Wang	12.5	222.9	72	Wang	18.5	209.4	108	Wang	27.5	175.3

This table is a combination of four tables: (1) Table 3 \Rightarrow 18 data by Jiao *et al.*,³ (2) Table 1 \Rightarrow 37 data by Ou *et al.*,⁷ (3) Table 1 \Rightarrow 19 data by Wang *et al.*¹¹ and (4) Table 4 \Rightarrow 34 data by Zhou *et al.*¹² These table numbers (3, 1, 1, 4) are the numbers used in the corresponding referenced papers.

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